

GOALS AND OBJECTIVES TRAINING OF CYCLING SPORTS

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ABSTRACT

In this scientific article, a study was conducted to identify the most effective interactive teaching methods in the course of training sessions on the subject "Theory and methodology of cycling" with students of the Uzbek State University of Physical Culture and Sports. Pedagogical recommendations are given on the use of active and interactive forms of classes for the formation and development of professional and pedagogical abilities of students.

Keywords: active and interactive methods, physical education, training, method, case study, development, strength, research, power load

Sports training is a process of physical education based on the use of physical exercises for the development and improvement of qualities and abilities that determine the athlete's readiness to achieve the highest performance. Training consists of many elements having a complex dynamic functional dependence, and is characterized by all the features of the process of training, education and expansion of the boundaries of the functional capabilities of the athlete's body. It is known that sports results directly depend on physical, technical, tactical and mental preparedness. Such a structure of preparedness is very conditional, since the organism is a single whole and these sides cannot be clearly distinguished. However this structure allows us to determine the main directions of improving the training process and systematize the available knowledge. In the process of sports training of cyclists, the following aspects of training are distinguished:

- physical training, which mainly contributes to the physical readiness of the athlete to demonstrate a certain sports result;
- technical and tactical training that ensures the development of cycling techniques, the study of the laws of wrestling, the development of ways to build it and practical use;
- mental training that provides the necessary motivational, ethical, intellectual and special mental foundations of a cyclist's activity.

At the same time, the content of sports training is considered in the aspect of general and special training of an athlete. Special training is understood as that part of it that is directly related to the tasks of sports specialization. Under general training is a part that, although it does not reveal a direct connection with the tasks of sports specialization, but creates essential prerequisites for sports improvement and is a component of the general system of education. For highly qualified athletes, the general training loses the meaning that it has at the early stages of sports improvement, and is specialized in nature, that is, it performs the role of auxiliary training.

Physical training of athletes is the process of improving motor qualities, manifested in the abilities

necessary in sports activities. This aspect of the athlete's training is determined by physical exertion affecting the cyclist's body, and therefore is associated with an increase in the functional capabilities of the body, versatile physical development. Thus, physical fitness is the most important component of

cycling sports training. The tasks of sports improvement are solved by applying physical loads that affect the cyclist's body and provide an increase in the functionality of his main systems. The main goal of training is to achieve optimal levels of various motor qualities by the athlete, taking into account their interrelation and interdependence at various stages of sports improvement.

Physical activity is characterized by:

1. the intensity of the work;
2. duration (volume) of work;
3. the duration of rest periods between the passage

Of the distance segments;

4. the nature of the rest period;
5. the number of repetitions.

A different combination of these components determines the direction and magnitude of the total impact of work on the body, that is, the magnitude of the load. Physical activity means the additional functional

activity of the body when performing physical exercises. The greater the magnitude of the load, the greater the fatigue of the body and shifts in the state of its functional systems involved in the performance of work. With this in mind, there are: loads of developmental impact (or actual training loads) that cause in significant changes in the athlete's body of a functional and structural nature; stabilizing loads, the primary purpose of which is to consolidate and improve the achieved adaptive reactions. You can judge the magnitude of the load by two groups of indicators. The first group is a quantitative expression of the training work performed, estimated by its externally expressed parameters (number of classes, duration in kilometers and hours,

number of repetitions, driving speed, pedaling pace, transmission value, etc.). To the second the group of indicators includes indicators of the body's response to this work - internal characteristics of the load.

The magnitude of the load can be estimated by the depth of fatigue caused by it. The higher the load, the greater the shifts in the state of the functional systems of the body and the degree of its fatigue. The degree of fatigue can be different - from obvious fatigue, accompanied by sharp shifts in the internal environment of the body and the forced refusal of the athlete from work, to hidden (compensated), when

compensatory mechanisms, with significant shifts in the internal environment provide high performance. The magnitude of the load is reflected in the nature and duration of the recovery period. After heavy loads, the recovery period is long and can last for several days, after small loads it is short-term.

The fact is that the performance of the same work by two cyclists may turn out to be a load of different severity for them, therefore, the internal manifestations will be different. Therefore, it is necessary to

clearly distinguish the concepts of work and workload – they are not synonymous. The load, even with its homogeneous structure, can cause various internal shifts in the body. It depends on individual performance at the time of training and environmental conditions: air temperature and humidity, wind strength and direction, track profile and coverage, altitude above sea level, quality of equipment, sportswear. The main types of loads used in the training of qualified athletes can be defined as follows.

A large load of a training session is characterized sharply pronounced functional shifts in the athlete's body, accompanied by a sharp decrease in performance and the appearance of symptoms of obvious fatigue. To create a large load, an athlete should be given such a volume of work that corresponds to his level of preparedness. The criterion of a heavy load is the athlete's inability to continue working in a given mode. A significant load is characterized by working in a stable condition, in which there is no decrease in performance. The work is 70-75% of the volume of work under heavy load.

The criterion of a significant load is the appearance of persistent signs of compensated fatigue. The average load is characterized by work amounting to 40-50% of the volume of work under heavy load, performed until signs of a violation of the stable state of the body appear. A small load is provided by the performance of work equal to 20-25% of the volume of work under heavy load. The criterion of low load is the coordinated activity of the musculoskeletal system, the functional systems of the body and the autonomic nervous system, that is, the formation of a stable state of working capacity. The amount of training load is derived from the intensity and volume of work. Their increase may occur simultaneously up to a certain point. In the future,

an increase in intensity leads to a decrease in volume and, conversely, an increase in the volume of work entails a forced decrease in its intensity. The amount of training load in a lesson is usually understood as the duration and total amount of work performed during a separate training session. When solving the problems of physical training of cyclists, various work is used duration: 5-7 s (100-200 m) - for sprinters; 30-60 s – for those specializing in the 1000 m race; 4-5 min - in individual and team pursuit; 2 h - in a team race on the highway; 4-5 h – in a group road race.

For the purpose, it is necessary to formulate requirements for sports performance and solve the following tasks:

- 1) Determine the model of sports result;
- 2) Present the athlete's model;
- 3) Identify the model of the preparation process.

The model of the preparation process includes:

- 1) Physical training
- 2) Technical training
- 3) Psychological training
- 4) Tactical training

Some patterns of sports training.

1. Unity of narrow specialization and focus on the maximum.
2. The unity of general and special training.
3. Continuity of the training process.
4. Gradual increase of training loads.
5. Wave-like nature of load dynamics.
6. The cyclical nature of the training process.

These patterns are based on well-known principles common to sports activities. Let's reveal the features of these principles in cycling. In sports, based on the previous principle, everything that is done in terms of the general training of an athlete should work for his narrow specialization.

There are 2 factors to consider here:

- 1) any exercise increases the level of physical fitness;
- 2) for a beginner, coordination of movement is improved in any exercises.

At the II stage, all reach the II-th category, and some – the I-th. At this stage, they develop the necessary physical qualities, but not those muscle groups and not in those modes.

	Initial preparation stage	The stage of initial specialized training	The stage of in-depth specialized training	The stage of the highest sportsmanship
Special training	indirect, non-specific effects 10%	Indirect specific effects 30%	Direct, specific effects 70 %	Local impacts 90 %
General preparation	90 %	70 %	30 %	10 %

At the III stage, everyone performs the 1st category, and the most gifted – MofS. all the motor units, only those that implement this motor act are loaded. Fatigue is the main training factor. Not all processes are restored in the same way. The mental state can change within 2-3 minutes, and the physical – 2-3

days. Therefore, the law of supercompensation works for each system separately. Systems that provide power and high-speed operation have a recovery time of about a day. With a rest of 2-3 days, the total effect will not work.

Optimal recovery time for various qualities (in hours):

Modes:	Developing	Supporting	Restoring
Power	24	36-48	72-96
Speed	24	36-48	72-96
Special Endurance	36-48	48-72	96 or more
Overall endurance	72-96	120	120

Athletes striving for high results. They train almost daily and even 2 times a day. The amount of training hours of highly qualified athletes in cycling reaches 30 hours per week. Physical training of cyclists is divided into general, auxiliary and special. Each type corresponds to specific means. The general physical training of a cyclist provides a versatile harmonious development of motor abilities, which, although they are not a consequence of the process of sports improvement in the chosen sport and are provided by non-specific means, but create prerequisites for further growth of results. Therefore, the planning of general physical training should be carried out taking into account specific requirements of the appropriate distance. It is unacceptable to use a method of physical training that ensures the growth of 179 physical qualities and functional properties, which contribute not only to improving the effectiveness of competitive activity, but also may limit the further development of special physical qualities that are significant for cyclists. Auxiliary physical training involves the

performance of work aimed at improving health and improving the speedy recovery of body systems after physical exertion, and also, creating opportunities for mastering the necessary amounts of training and competitive loads characteristic of cycling. Special physical training is the improvement of those special motor qualities and functional capabilities of the body that meet the requirements of competitive activity in the chosen form of racing.

Regardless of the type of racing, an athlete has to comprehensively demonstrate various motor qualities, but in different ratios. For example, specializing in pursuit races in training in classes on the highway and track, the main attention should be paid to the education of general and special endurance.

To improve the speed capabilities in pursuit races, it is necessary to widely use the means and methods of sprint training, combining them with participation in competitions on the sprint program. For the education of strength qualities use a variety of means (riding on high gears, acceleration uphill, classes with weights, etc.). High level of endurance cyclists specializing in in pursuit races, they also support in the competitive period, using for this purpose the means of road training and participation in competitions on the highway. Cyclists specializing in highway racing, along with endurance training, devote a significant part of their time to improving their speed and strength capabilities. Low indicators of speed and strength qualities, even if there is a high level of development of endurance and speed qualities, become one of the reasons for the unsuccessful performance of racers at the World Championships.

When preparing riders, depending on the training periods, strength, general and special endurance should be developed in the preparatory period; speed and speed-strength abilities – in the competitive. According to experts working with qualified cyclists, depending on the training period, the ratio between general and special training changes significantly. The problem of psychological preparation is one of the most important in the training process of athletes. It is difficult to determine with high accuracy the weight of physical and mental qualities in achieving athletic results, but it is absolutely indisputable that in a sports competition a considerable share belongs to mental factors. A person's character is a complex mental property of a person, a set of basic mental traits that leave an imprint on behavior and actions. Character formation is associated with the development of a worldview, views, beliefs. Firm beliefs are the basis of a firm character. A strong character, will can be formed on the basis of the nervous system of any force. The art of a coach is to prepare an athlete to achieve high results as a result of many years of comprehensive improvement of mental and physical activity. For a successful performance in various races, an athlete needs not only an incentive, but also faith in his own strength. This is facilitated by a high level of fitness, the degree of versatile special and physical fitness, the determination to give all the

strength to fight, maximize your capabilities. This characterizes the psychological readiness for competition.

The crown of all psychological preparation should be considered a state of mental readiness, which manifests itself in the maximum mobilization of the cyclist to achieve the highest performance in competitions. Therefore, psychological preparation should be presented as a continuous process of educating an athlete throughout his sports activity, characterized by the ability to introspect, the ability

to objectively assess the positive and negative sides of his opponents, to understand tactical situations, the ability to overcome difficulties, show restraint and self-control. It takes a long time to study the mental characteristics of an athlete, to observe his behavior during training, competitions, at an educational institution or during work, in public activities. Psychological training of cyclists in the annual cycle goes through four stages: perspective-training, pre-start, starting, post-competitive (inter-competitive). The role of the coach at the perspective-training stage of preparation is especially great. He is not only an organizer of training, but also an educator in the true sense of the word. It is easy for a coach who knows how to win the love and respect of his students to get them to follow his advice and instructions. Athletes' faith in the coach sometimes becomes one of the important factors contributing to sports success. As the observations of our leading cyclists show, many have been actively competing at a high level for no more than 7 – 8 years. The early retirement of racers from the sport, the drop in their results are primarily due to mental exhaustion and overwork of the central nervous system. In order to prolong the athletic longevity of a cyclist, training should be built emotionally and in a variety of ways. In each training session, new things should appear in the development of technical and tactical elements.

The results of the study. Solving two tasks in one training session: functional and technical or functional and tactical – distracts the cyclist from the monotonous heavy and prolonged load. A significant effect in the training process can be achieved only when, against the background of general fatigue, specific difficult work is performed for speed or for remote endurance. According to such work, coaches often draw conclusions about the possibility of an athlete's participation in further races. Therefore, the coach should not disclose the entire training plan, knowing that athletes will unwittingly spare themselves in the first half of the class, trying to save strength to perform the most important final work. To encourage athletes to systematic training, to new sporting achievements, they often use various mottos, sayings, slogans. As a psychological method, this undoubtedly has a certain effect on the athlete. Experience has shown that the presence of spectators at training, their cheering shouts, chanting slogans have a positive effect on sports achievements. To reduce fatigue after training,

competitions and autogenic and psycho-regulatory training is used to restore athletic performance. In addition, it is used for increased emotional arousal, to mobilize readiness for maximum athletic tension. To master this method, you need to practice systematically for about 2-3 months (2-3 times a day for 10-12 minutes). Initially, the classes are conducted by a doctor or coach. Each season, as well as the main stages of sports training, should be completed with a visit to a physical education dispensary for comprehensive examination. This makes it possible to identify deviations in health and functional status in time and carry out appropriate preventive treatment. On the track in sprint races, cyclists have to take several starts in one day, despite their injuries. All this requires tremendous willpower from the athlete. Fearlessness before falling should be brought up from the very first training sessions on a bicycle. In addition to a coach and a doctor, more experienced riders help novice racers overcome this psychological barrier.

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, further improvement of management technology in basketball should be associated with the study of the basic laws of the formation of the level of special preparedness of basketball players in the process of age development, as well as the formation of sports uniforms in structural formations, the purpose of which is

the direct preparation of players and teams in general for responsible games. As is well known, modern views in the field of athlete training management are not based on mechanical division the training process is divided into parts (stages, cycles, periods), and on the natural biological laws of the adaptation of the athletes' body to specific conditions, which ultimately underlie the conceptual provisions of the theory of sports and its components such as the periodization of training, the development of athletic form.

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